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RETAIL MARKET SECTOR: RECENT TRENDS AND DIRECTION FOR INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides detailed information about prospectus and growth of retail sector in India: a study of emerging issue has been discussed keeping in view the changing economic environment of the Indian economy. As the modern-day retail sector in India is reflected in sprawling shopping centers, multiplex- malls and huge complexes offer shopping, entertainment and food all under one roof, the concept of shopping has altered in terms of format and consumer buying behavior, ushering in a revolution in shopping in India. This has also contributed to large-scale investments in the real estate sector with major national and global players investing in developing the infrastructure and construction of the retailing business. The trends that are driving the growth of the retail sector in India. The sector contributes 10 per cent of the GDP and is estimated to show 20 per cent annual growth rate by the end of the decade as against the current growth rate of 8.5 per cent. This paper concludes with the likely impact of the entry of global players into the Indian retailing industry. It also highlights the challenges faced by the retail industry in near future.

Key words: Retail Industry, Global players, GDP, Retail Markets etc.

Introduction

India is being seen as a potential goldmine for retail investors from all over the world and latest research has rated India as the top destination for retailers for an attractive emerging retail market. India is vast a middle class and their almost untapped retail markets are key attractions for global retail giants wanting to enter newer markets. Even though India has well over 5 million retail outlets, the country sorely lacks anything that can resemble a retailing industry in the modern sense. The Retail Industry in India has come forth as one of the most dynamic and fast paced industries with several players entering the market. But all of them have not yet tasted success because of the heavy initial investments that are required to break even with other companies and compete with other companies.

Retailing in India is one of the pillars of its economy and accounts for 14 to 15 percent of its GDP. The Indian retail market is estimated to be US\$ 500 billion and one of the top five retail markets in the world by economic value. India is one of the fastest growing retail markets in the world, with 1.2 billion people.

The India Retail Industry is gradually inching its way towards becoming the next boom in industry. The accelerated growth in the Indian economy, changing buying behavior of the customer, increase in disposable income of middle class, infrastructure development, increasing urbanization, credit availability, increasing investments in technology and real estate boom are all the reasons for the maturing of simple retailing into a more microscopic and systematized process. According to Kotler (1972), "Retailing includes all the activities involved in selling goods and services directly to the final customers". Retail is the word which originates from a French-Italian word "retailer". It means someone who cuts off or sheds a small piece from something. It includes activities of marketing and selling products or services to end consumers for their household or personal use. Retailer is a Person or an Agent or a Company or an Organization who is instrumental in reaching the Goods or Merchandise or Services to the end User or Ultimate Consumer.

This presents international retailing specialists with a great opportunity. The organized retail sector is expected to grow stronger than GDP growth in the next five years driven by changing lifestyles, burgeoning income and favorable demographic outline. Indian retail is expected to grow 25 per cent annually. Modern retail in India could be worth US\$ 175-200 billion by 2016. The Food Retail Industry in India dominates the shopping basket. The Mobile phone Retail Industry in India is already a US\$ 16.7 billion business, growing at over 20 per cent per year. The future of the India Retail Industry looks promising with the growth of the market, with the government policies becoming more favorable and the emerging technologies facilitating operations. In the year 2014, retail sector has reached 14th rank in Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) > USD 500 billion total retail sales eight per cent Organized Retail Sector Penetration (ORSP) > 20 per cent growth in organized retail during 2012-2020.

Objectives of the Study

Main objectives of the study are as follows:

- To understand the evolution of retail sector in India
- To review the Retail Sector Structure and growth perceptiveness in India.

- To know the Recent Trends, Challenges and Developmental aspects of Retail Sector in India

Methodology of the study:

This study is basically exploratory in nature. An extensive review of literature has been undertaken in order to assimilate the facts pertaining to current state in the India's Retail scenario. An attempt has been made to identify upcoming areas for retail investment and future trends in retailing. This paper is attempting to contribute meaningfully to existing literature on Indian retail industry and aims to guide business managers in finding their way out through the retail maze in India.

Collection of Data:

The present study is based on primary and the secondary data. Secondary data which is extracted from the survey reports i.e. The Economic Times, Times of India, India Today, retail sector segmental reports and other reports has been taken. Primary data has been collected by from officials through personal interview, interaction and questionnaire method.

Review of Literature

To present a brief review of literature carried out by different individual researchers and institutions on Retailing in India. Discussed here under Retailing is an occupation came into existence when farmers started producing more food than they required. Different people had different skill sets, and people who had a surplus of one kind of good desired the goods they did not have or could not produce (Pradhan, 2007). In India, it is observed that the existence of the current kirana format and other shops can be traced to the Manusmriti and Kautilya's Arthashastra. While, Kautilya commented on the location of stores dealing in specific products in a city; the Indian history and archeology records reveals the existence of markets during the Harappan civilization also.

In terms of retail institutions, it was mainly mom and pop stores (Kiranas stores) run by individuals and the wet markets, mandis, melasor bazaar. There were also government run public distribution shops as well as different co-operative stores. All these stores had counter-service and self-service was not a feasible option. Multi-brand retailers came into the picture and organized retail industry not just evolved but beautifully bloomed. Until 1990's, the industry was dominated by the unorganized sector. It was a market dominated by sellers with limited number of brands, and little choice available to customers. Lack of trained manpower, lax laws and government regulations all discouraged the growth of organized retailing in India during

that period (Sharma, 2009). It has been reported that things soon changed and the winds started blowing in favor of the retail sector in the year 1995 and the millennium year saw the grand entry of supermarkets and hypermarkets (The Economic Times 2008).

Growth of Retail Sector in India:

Retail and real estate are the two booming sectors of India in the present times. And if industry experts are to be believed, the prospects of both the sectors are mutually dependent on each other. Retail, one of India's largest industries, has presently emerged as one of the most dynamic and fast paced industries of our times with several players entering the market. Accounting for up to 15 per cent of the country's GDP and around ten per cent of the employment retailing in India is gradually inching its way toward becoming the next boom industry.

Evolution of Retail Sector in India:

- ❖ Traditionally retailing in India can be traced to the emergence of the neighborhood Kirana stores catering to the convenience of the consumers.
- ❖ Era of government support for rural retail: Indigenous franchise model of store chains run by Khadi & Village Industries Commission.
- ❖ 1980s experienced slow change as India began to open up economy.
- ❖ Textiles sector with companies like Bombay Dyeing, Raymond's, S. Kumar's and Grasim first saw the emergence of retail chains.
- ❖ Later than successfully created an organized retailing concept and established a series of showrooms for its premium watches.
- ❖ The latter half of the 1990s saw a fresh wave of entrants with a shift from Manufactures to Pure Retailers. For e.g. Food World, Subiksina and Nilgiris in food and FMCG; Planet M and Music World in music; Crossword and Fountrinhend in books.
- ❖ Post 1995 onwards saw an emergence of shopping centers.
- ❖ Mainly in urban areas, with facilities like car parking.
- ❖ Targeted to provide a complete destination experience for all segments of society.
- ❖ Emergence of hyper and super markets trying to provide consumer with 3 "V's" i.e. Value, Variety and Volume.

- ❖ Expanding target consumer segment: The Sachet revolution - example of reaching to the bottom of the pyramid.
- ❖ At year end of 2000 the size of the Indian organized retail industry is estimated at ` 13,000 crores.

Figure: 1

Retail market in India

The Indian retail market is estimated to exceed US\$ 750 billion by 2015, according to the India Retail Report 2013 (IRIS Research), presenting a strong potential for foreign retailers planning to enter India. According to A. T. Kearney's Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2012, India is the 5th most favorable destination for international retailers. Of the total Indian retail market, eight per cent constitutes the organized retail segment which is estimated to grow at a rate of almost 30 per cent by 2015, and hence at a much faster pace than the overall retail market which is forecast to grow by 16per cent in the same period. Until 2011, the Indian Central Government denied Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in multi-brand retail, forbidding foreign groups from any ownership in supermarkets, convenience stores or other retail outlets. In late 2012, the Government of India passed a Foreign Direct Investment policy which allows foreign retailers to own up to 51 per cent in multi-brand retail and 100 per cent in single brand retail.

The introduction of the FDI in retail policy will impact the availability of talent. Many institutes have now introduced specialized post graduate degrees in retail management, i.e. approximately 6,000 qualified professionals with expertise in the field of retail management are being trained every year. Until now, retailers have sponsored courses in some of the top B-schools to attract talent at a junior level, while hiring at a mid to senior level has primarily been from competitors.

We believe that the current trends and the rapid growth of the market will create an acute shortage of talent at the mid to senior level, creating high demand for candidates that are experienced in setting up large retail chains as well as candidates with international exposure. This increase in demand is likely to drive up salaries. The figure below illustrates the inflation rate in India over the last 5 years; consequently average annual increase in salary will be between 12-18 per cent in the retail sector as a result of skill shortages spurred by the entry of new foreign players. In addition, salary increases are likely to go up by 20-25per cent.

Issues and challenges of Retail Sector in India

The organized retail sector in India has been witnessing various issues and challenges which are proving to be a hurdle for its fast-paced growth. Even though the organized retail sector is in a very nascent stage in India, it provides ample opportunities for retailers, and mitigation of a few challenges will help the sector attain higher economies of scale and growth. Elucidated below are the challenges and risks that the sector faces:

- ❖ Global economic slowdown
- ❖ Competition from the unorganised sector
- ❖ Retail sector has no recognition as an industry
- ❖ High real-estate costs
- ❖ Lack of basic infrastructure
- ❖ Supply-chain inefficiencies
- ❖ Challenges with respect to human resources
- ❖ Margin Pressure

Government Initiatives

The Government of India has allowed 51 per cent FDI in Multi-Brand Retail Trading (MBRT) and 100 per cent in Single-Brand Retail Trading (SBRT). According to the extant policy, foreign retailers investing more than 51 per cent can open outlets across the country on the condition that 30 per cent of their sourced sales would come from small to medium-sized domestic enterprises. Further, global chains will now need to invest only 50 per cent of the initial compulsory investment of US\$ 100 million in setting up cold storages and warehouses in India.

Foreign chains have been given the green signal to set up stores in cities with a population of less than one million. Earlier, supermarkets could

only commence their operations in 53 cities, the ones with a population of more than a million. The Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) has approved Swedish clothing major Hennes & Mauritz AB's (H&M) proposal to open 50 stores across the country with an investment of Rs 720 crore (US\$ 116.20 million). Earlier this year, the Cabinet Committee on Economic Affairs (CCEA) had cleared a Rs 10,500 crore (US\$ 1.69 billion) proposal by IKEA.

Recent Trends of Retail Sector in India

- ❖ Retailing in India is witnessing a huge revamping exercise as can be seen in the graph
- ❖ India is rated the fifth most attractive emerging retail market; a potential goldmine.
- ❖ Estimated to be US\$ 200 billion, of which organized retailing (i.e. modern trade) makes up 3 percent or US\$ 6.4 billion
- ❖ As per a report by KPMG the annual growth of department stores is estimated at 24per cent
- ❖ Ranked second in a Global Retail Development Index of 30 developing countries drawn up by AT Kearney.
- ❖ Multiple drivers leading to a consumption boom:
 - Favorable demographics
 - Growth in income
 - Increasing population of women
 - Raising aspirations: Value added goods sales
- ❖ Food and apparel retailing key drivers of growth
- ❖ Organized retailing in India has been largely an urban income households.
- ❖ Phenomenon with affluent classes and growing number of double-income households.
- ❖ More successful in cities in the south and west of India. Reasons range from differences in consumer buying behavior to cost of real estate and taxation laws.
- ❖ Rural markets emerging as a huge opportunity for retailers reflected in the share of the rural market across most categories of consumption

- ITC is experimenting with retailing through its e-Choupal and Choupalsagar in rural hypermarkets.
 - HLL is using its Project Shakti initiative is leveraging women self-help groups to explore the rural market.
 - Mahanaza is leveraging technology and network marketing concepts to act as an aggregator and serve the rural markets.
- ❖ IT is a tool that has been used by retailers ranging from Amazon.com to ebay to radically change buying behavior across the globe.

India is being seen as a potential goldmine for retail investors from over the world and latest research has rated India as the top destination for retailers for an attractive emerging retail market. India is vast middle class and its almost untapped retail industry is key attractions for global retail giants wanting to enter newer markets. Even though India has well over 5 million retail outlets, the country sorely lacks anything that can resemble a retailing industry in the modern sense of the term. This presents international retailing specialists with a great opportunity. The organized retail sector is expected to grow stronger than GDP growth in the next five years driven by changing lifestyles, burgeoning income and favorable demographic outline.

Retail Industry Market Structure

The Indian retail market currently stands at USD 396 billion and is likely to grow further at 12per cent to increase to USD 574billion by 2015. This sector is the second largest employer after agriculture, employing more than 35 million people with wholesale trade generating an additional employment to 5.50 million more. The growing disposable income in the country is resulting in increasing consumer spending habits i.e. axes and overheads. With competition increasing in the retail sector, these players are slowly transforming themselves into an organized set-up. The characteristic features of both organized and unorganized retailers in India include:

Unorganized retailers: Traditional or unorganized retail outlets are normally street markets, counter stores, kiosks and vendors, where the ownership and management rest with one person only. This sector accounts for two thirds of the market and requires low skilled labor. These are highly competitive outlets, with negligible rental costs, cheap labour and low taxes and overheads. With competition increasing in the retail sector, these players are slowly transforming themselves into an organized set-up.

Organized retailers: Organized retailing comprises mainly of modern retailing within busy shopping malls, multi storied malls and huge

complexes that offer a large variety of products in terms of quality, value for money and makes shopping a memorable experience.

Figure: 2

Findings and conclusion:

This study presents the major findings of the Retail Sector Industry growth and challenges in India the following observations were found, which are discussed here under:

- ❖ It is observed that Indian retail has been changing its contours since the time of inception.
- ❖ A simple activity of selling in small markets to a more sophisticated task of bidding on-line, retailing has showcased several successful forms and facets.
- ❖ India's capacity to embrace new formats is incredible and the customer's interest to shop at new avenues is insatiable.
- ❖ A young nation with over 60 per cent of the population within the age of 35 years is pushing on the need for more retail activity in India.
- ❖ It is observed that the emerging Indian consumers are not just time pressed but also style starved.
- ❖ It can be seen the roads to India's retail are getting even more attractive with the government initiating FDI in Indian retail sector. Food and apparel retailing key drivers of growth
- ❖ Organized retailing in India has been largely an urban
- ❖ The Government of India has allowed 51 per cent FDI in Multi-Brand Retail Trading (MBRT) and 100 per cent in Single-Brand Retail Trading (SBRT).

As we agreed, India's retail sector industry is an important sector for Indian economic growth. The Retail industry in India has come forth as one of the most dynamic and fast paced industries with several players entering the market. The major challenge of this sector is transition includes internationalization, cross cultures, strategic alliances, partnership & mergers are *global players* of retail trading promotion. Further, it is concluded that Retailing in India is growing at a frenzied pace. The relatively low rates of penetration of organized retail in most categories coupled with sheer attractiveness of India's demographic and economic environment is expected to continue to add momentum to overall prospects of this sector in the long term. The organized retail sector is expected to grow stronger than GDP growth in the next five years driven by changing lifestyles, burgeoning income and favorable demographic outline.

Suggestions for retail sector in India:

Many agencies have estimated differently about the size of organized retail market in 2011. The one thing that is common amongst these estimates is that Indian organized retail market will be very big in 2011. The status of the retail industry will depend mostly on external factors like Government regulations and policies and real estate prices, besides the activities of retailers and demands of the customers also show impact on retail industry. As the retail market place changes shape and competition increases, the potential for improving retail productivity and cutting costs is likely to decrease. Therefore it is important for retailers to secure a distinctive position in the market place based on values relationships or experience. Finally, it is important to note that these strategies are not strictly independent of each other value is function of not just price quality and service but can also be enhanced by personalization and offering a memorable experience.

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